

Studies on Acid Dissociation Equilibria of 2-[(1*H*-Benzimidazol-2-ylmethylene)amino]benzoic Acid in Various Aquo-organic Media

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A new Schiff base, 2-[(1*H*-benzimidazol-2-ylmethylene)amino]benzoic acid has been synthesised and characterised by spectral and analytical data. The acid dissociation constants of the Schiff base have been determined *pH*-metrically using the Irving-Rossotti titration technique. The influence of ionic strength, temperature and solvent on the acid dissociation equilibria of COOH and NH groups has been studied. A comparison of ΔH and ΔS in different aquo-organic media reveals that the positive ΔS is the main driving force in the acid dissociation processes of these groups. The effect of solvent was discussed in the light of solute-solvent interactions in various aquo-organic mixtures.

SOLVENT effect on the *pK_a* values of a number of oxygenated acids (HA), like hydroxylic and carboxylic acids¹⁻³ showed a linear relationship with mole-fraction of the organic solvent. Conversely, nitrogenous^{4,5} bases (cationic acids, BH⁺), like anilines, pyridines and amines showed a reverse trend. Thus, in passing from water to high percentage of organic solvent, the strengths of the former acids become weaker while those of the latter stronger. Analogous trends were observed with the effect of ionic strength on these groups⁶. However, little work is reported on the effect of solvent and ionic strength on the acid dissociation reactions of the compounds that contain both these groups, and also on the synergistic behaviour of these groups. These studies are of interest in correlating the acid strengths in different solvent media. As benzimidazoles and Schiff bases are becoming increasingly important as biochemical, analytical and antimicrobial reagents, the Schiff base, 2-[(1*H*-benzimidazol-2-ylmethylene)-amino] benzoic acid [BMABA] was chosen for this purpose.

Experimental

The Schiff base, BMABA was prepared by refluxing (6 h) equimolar quantities (2 mmol) of benzimidazol-2-carboxaldehyde and anthranilic acid in ethanol (150 ml) containing 1 g sodium acetate. Pale yellow crystals separated on cooling in ice were filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol (5%) and repeatedly crystallised from ethanol to get a tlc pure product, m.p. 182° (Found : C, 67.02 ; H, 4.35 ; N, 15.55. C₁₅H₁₁N₃O₂ requires C, 67.83 ; H, 4.15 ; N, 15.85%). ν_{\max} (KBr) 3250 br (NH), 2550-2700 (OH), 1690 (C=O), 1630 and 1600 cm⁻¹ (C=N) ; δ (60 MHz ; CDCl₃ ; TMS internal reference) 8.0 (s, 1H, HC=N), 7.45 (m, 8H, ArH). Based on

the above data, structure I was assigned to the Schiff base.

The acid dissociation constants were determined using the Irving-Rossotti *pH*-titration technique⁷, (i) at 20, 25, 30 and 40° in 50% and 70% v/v aq. dioxane, (ii) at I=0.03, 0.05, 0.10, 0.15 M (NaClO₄) in 50% v/v aq. dioxane at 30°, (iii) in 40, 50, 60 and 70% v/v aq. dioxane at 30°, and (iv) in 70% v/v aq. ethanol, aq. methanol, aq. isopropanol and aq. acetone at 30°. The experimental details were those described earlier^{9,10}. The calorimetric measurements were made adopting the reported procedures^{11,12}.

Results and Discussion

In the acid region, the ligand titration curve lies above the acid curve due to the basic property of the ligand nitrogens to accept protons from strongly acidic medium. However, in the basic region, it lies below the acid curve due to the release of COOH protons and hence the number of dissociable protons in the neutral molecule is one.

From the *pH*-titration curves, the values of \bar{n}_H were evaluated using Irving-Rossotti method⁷. Proton-ligand formation curves were obtained by plotting *pH* vs \bar{n}_H . From these curves (0.13 < \bar{n}_H < 1.96), the values of *pK_{a1}*, and *pK_{a2}* were evaluated by various computational techniques⁸ and the values

were in agreement with each other. The standard deviations are within ± 0.01 pK_a units.

The values of pK_{a1} correspond to the proton of the tertiary nitrogen (pyridyl group) of the benzimidazole ring^{9,10} and those of pK_{a2} correspond to the proton of the COOH group. Dissociation of the imino proton of the imidazole ring was not observed even after pH 12.8. It was observed that the pK_{NH} values in 2-[(1*H*-benzimidazol-2-ylmethylene)amino]-phenol [BMAP]⁹ is higher when compared to BMABA. This may be due to the base strengthening mesomeric effect of phenolic-OH in BMAP. Conversely, in BMABA, the COOH group exerts a base weakening inductive ($-I$) effect on the other groups of the molecule. As a consequence, the basicity of azomethine nitrogen is lowered to such an extent ($pK_a < 1.5$) that practically it showed no uptake of protons even from highly acidic medium.

Effect of ionic strength: A perusal of the data (Table 1) indicates that the values of pK_{COOH} decrease while pK_{NH} increase on increasing ionic strength. This is in conformity with the observations made on typical weak acids and bases (cationic acids), respectively^{3,6}. In an acid dissociation reaction, the COOH group produces a negatively charged species from a neutral molecule while a basic group like NH^+ produces a neutral molecule from a positively charged (cationic) species. Thus, it can be concluded that

the molecule tends to remain in ionic form in a medium of high ionic strength. Linear plots were observed between \sqrt{I} and either pK_{NH} or pK_{COOH} .

Effect of temperature: It was observed that the pK_{COOH} and pK_{NH} values decrease (Table 1) with an increase in temperature, suggesting that the dissociation reactions are favourable at higher temperatures. The thermodynamic parameters, viz. ΔG , ΔH and ΔS associated with the proton dissociation reactions were calculated utilizing the standard equations and are presented in Table 2. The ΔH values were also evaluated from simple calorimetric measurements and are consistent with those obtained from pH -metric data. The positive values of ΔG suggest that the proton dissociation reactions are not spontaneous. Further, the positive enthalpy change showed the endothermic nature of these reactions. Further, the ΔH values are almost constant in both 50% and 70% (v/v) aqueous dioxane. This is expected because the strength of the proton-ligand bond is essentially the same in both of these media. A comparison of the ΔH and ΔS terms in 50% and 70% (v/v) aqueous dioxane reveals that it is the positive entropy change which is the main driving force in these dissociation processes. Therefore, the difference in pK_a values must be an

TABLE 1—ACID DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF BMABA

Solvent=50% v/v aq. dioxane			
Temp. °C	I(NaClO ₄) M	pK_{COOH}	pK_{NH}
20	0.1	7.15	3.99
25	0.1	6.90	3.88
	0.00	6.95	3.42
	0.03	6.71	3.63
30	0.05	6.63	3.68
	0.10	6.56	3.72
	0.15	6.50	3.76
40	0.10	5.98	3.46
Temp=30°, I=0.10 M NaClO ₄			
Solvent %v/v	$1/\epsilon \times 10^3$	pK_{COOH}	pK_{NH}
40 D-W	2.427	6.35	3.71
50 D-W	3.053	6.56	3.72
60 D-W	4.082	6.87	3.66
70 D-W	5.814	7.22	3.60
70 A-W	2.649	7.03	4.02
70 M-W	2.165	6.51	4.15
70 E-W	2.517	6.67	3.94
70 I-W	3.195	6.81	3.89

D=dioxane, A=acetone, M=methanol, I=isopropanol, W=water.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS ASSOCIATED WITH ACID DISSOCIATION EQUILIBRIA OF BMABA

	Dioxane % v/v	pK_{COOH}	pK_{NH}
ΔG (30°)	50	38.07	21.59
ΔG mol ⁻¹	70	41.88	20.88
ΔH	50	104.48	47.82
ΔH mol ⁻¹	70	104.98	48.24
ΔS	50	219.24	86.65
ΔS mol ⁻¹ deg ⁻¹	70	207.19	91.00

entropy effect due to varying degree of solvation in different aquo-organic media.

Effect of solvent: The pK_{COOH} values increase with an increase in the dioxane content of the solvent mixture. Plot of pK_{COOH} vs mole-fraction (X_2) of dioxane was linear while that against $1/\epsilon$ showed a curvature. However, the initial points invariably fell on a straight line while the latter points, corresponding to low dielectric constant, deviated from it. Similar observations were made on a number of carboxylic acids^{2,12}. This may be due to non-electrostatic forces that come into operation in the media of high organic content, where a change in the structuredness of the solvent occurs¹³.

Solvent composition has little influence on the acid dissociation equilibria of the pyridyl (NH^+) group. On passing from 40% to 70% v/v dioxane, it becomes 0.11 pK_a unit stronger. No linear plots were obtained between pK_{NH} and either X_2 or $1/\epsilon$. Similar observations were made with the acid dissociation equilibria of a number of cationic acids like anilines⁴ and pyridines⁵. Such a reversal of the solvent effect on the pK_{NH} values when compared to pK_{COOH} may be due to the following solute-solvent interactions¹⁴ in mixed-solvent systems. Δn

increase in the organic content of the solvent system results in a decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium. This will increase the electrostatic (ion-ion) interaction between a proton and a negatively charged oxygen atom to a greater extent than the ion-dipole interaction between the proton and the solvent. Thus, as dielectric constant decreases, the value of pK_a increases for proton-ligand system containing O-H bonds. Conversely, an increase in the organic content of the solvent would be expected to increase the ion-dipole forces between a proton and a N-atom in the ligand to a lesser extent than the ion-dipole forces between a proton and the more electro-negative O-atom of the solvent. Therefore, a decrease in the value of pK_{NH} would be expected for compounds containing N-H bonds.

In 70% v/v mixed solvents, the pK_{COOH} values are in the order, dioxane > acetone > isopropanol > ethanol > methanol.

However, in the case of pK_{NH} values, the order is dioxane < isopropanol < ethanol < acetone < methanol. Except the position of acetone-water system, this is in conformity with the sequence of $1/\epsilon$ in these mixed solvents. The reversal of the position of acetone system may be due to its smaller proton solvation.

The degree of formation (α) of different protonated and non-protonated species as a function of pH was calculated using the expressions¹⁻³

$$\alpha_{A^-} = \frac{1}{1 + [H^+]/K_{COOH} + [H^+]^2/K_{NH} \cdot K_{COOH}} \quad (1)$$

$$\alpha_{HA} = \frac{[H^+]/K_{COOH}}{1 + [H^+]/K_{COOH} + [H^+]^2/K_{NH} \cdot K_{COOH}} \quad (2)$$

$$\alpha_{H_2A^+} = \frac{[H^+]^2/K_{NH} \cdot K_{COOH}}{1 + [H^+]/K_{COOH} + [H^+]^2/K_{NH} \cdot K_{COOH}} \quad (3)$$

The same were graphically represented as distribution diagrams (Fig. 1). It can be seen that the proportions of H_2A^+ and A^- change monotonically with pH, whereas the intermediate species, HA attains a certain maximum. Thus, H_2A^+ exists upto pH 5.0, HA between pH 2.5 to 7.5, and A^- above pH 5.5 in significant proportions.

Fig. 1. Distribution diagram for BMABA.

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